

Situation of Some Factors Affecting Case Management Activities for People with Disabilities in Da Nang

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ABSTRACT: The study was conducted on 167 case managers for people with disabilities in many wards, communes, and social work centers in Da Nang. Weakness of service providers, shortage of resources for assistance, qualifications of case managers are the factors that affect the process and performance of case management service for the disabled, especially important services for people with disabilities such as health and educational services. On the other hand, there has not been a clear mechanism for coordinating services and resources to help people with disabilities in Da Nang. Case management for people with disabilities should be put into operation by social workers at all levels by the management of Department of Labor, Invalids and Social Affairs. The Ministry of Labor, Invalids and Social Affairs needs to promulgate procedures and regulations on the responsibilities of case managers.

KEYWORDS: Case Management; case manager; people with disabilities

1. INTRODUCTION

People with disabilities get a special attention from the Vietnamese Communist Party and State, occupying the central position in the national social welfare system. Over the years, the state has been focusing on the comprehensive care and support for people with disabilities, from education and health policies to social protection and integration policies etc. The Vietnamese Law on People with Disabilities was promulgated and implemented into activities to help people with disabilities and has gained encouraging results. However, assisting people with disabilities needs the coordination and efforts of many different departments, branches, organizations, agencies, and the whole society. In that context, social work, with its characteristics plays an important role in promoting comprehensive coordination of the assisting process for people with disabilities. Finding a suitable social work methodology will support a lot in helping people with disabilities in our country .

Case management is one of the methods of social work practice and is widely applied in the global social work context to help the underprivileged. However, this is a new issue for Vietnam, both in theory and in practice. Theoretically, there have not been many studies in our country focusing on this issue at a large scale such as dissertations or projects at ministerial or state level, but only in a narrow scope such as case management at a center, a district. In practice, the implementation of case management for individuals has not really taken place at the local level, at any agency in a systematic way and carries the true nature of case management. Therefore, clarifying the theoretical issues of Case Management such as its purpose, philosophy, procedures ... is an urgent requirement for the social work in Vietnam. On the other hand, practical activities of Case Management such as organizational methods, implementation techniques, the role of social workers on this field when assisting disadvantaged people, especially on the characteristics of Vietnamese people with disabilities is a very important issue that needs to be studied and understood.

2. RESEARCH RESULTS

The main research subjects are 167 case managers of people with disabilities in wards, communes and social work centers in Da Nang. The studied area is the situation of all districts of Da Nang city and the measures applied on Hai Chau district.

After the data is collected, the results are processed by SPSS program of Window system, version 22.0. We use a statistical technique that is to analyze the reliability by Cronbach's Alpha coefficient method, in order to determine the reliability of the scales in the questionnaire.

This model evaluates the reliability of the measurement based on the calculation of the variance of each item in each scale, the total measurement and the correlation of each item with the scores of the remaining items on each scale and of the whole measurement. The reliability of each subscale is considered low if the coefficient has the result of $\alpha < 0.4$.

The pilot survey’s output shows that the reliability of the scale is relatively high and allows for a more formal investigation. The official survey’s result on 167 case managers showing the reliability of the case management of the disabled is presented in the following table.

Table 1. Reliability of case management task scales for people with disabilities by the case managers

Scales	Alpha coefficient
<i>Basic case management tasks</i>	
1. Information gathering	0,621
2. Assessment of needs	0,744
3. Plan for the supportive activities	0,947
4. Implement the plan	0,708
5. Follow up, review and end case management	0.752

Status of professional knowledge

The knowledge of the case managers is critical to the success of the cases being helped, if the case manager does not have a professional background in case management, about people with disabilities. Those who implements case management need to be equipped with knowledge on case management in a systematic way. The basic knowledge that a case manager needs is knowledge of the social system, of human psychology, ethical principles and regulations in case management. The case managers should need have knowledge on disability area, about people with disabilities, policies for people with disabilities, etc. This is difficult, however, in the current context of Vietnam, there is no formal and complete training program for case management in general and for case managers in particular, so the qualifications of the case manager has been limited.

Table 2. Trained professional knowledge of case managers

Manifestations	medium score	Level	Answer (%)				
			Totally disagree	Basically disagree	Partially agree	Agree basically	Totally agree
I am equipped with case management knowledge in a methodical and systematic way	3.12	2	0	16.4	21.3	35.8	26.5
I have in-depth knowledge of social systems	2.8	first	6	12.4	25.6	34.8	21.2
I understand very well about disability and people with disabilities	4.29	5	0	0	14.3	38.5	47.2
I understand very well the issues of policies and laws in helping people with disabilities	4.18	4	0	0	16.5	52.7	30.8
Knowledge group	3.59						

The results shown in Table 3.7 show that, in general, the trained professional knowledge of case managers occupy an average level with an average score of 3.59. This number is not a good representation for the professional knowledge of case managers. There is a disparity among different case managers’ professional knowledge. Knowledge about people with disabilities has the

highest score, occupying 47.2% who say that they understand very well, while the average score is 4.29. In contrast, knowledge on the social system only gets a score of 2.8. In fact, this type of knowledge is important in case management. It is, in fact, the knowledge on the family system and its impact on individuals, the impact of the social welfare system on the individuals. Knowledge of policy and legal issues in assisting people with disabilities has a fairly high average score, which is 4.18. This is the basic knowledge to help case managers providing assistance to people with disabilities.

Thirdly, the type of knowledge "I am equipped with systematic and systematic case management knowledge" is low with an average score of 3.12. Equipping methodically on case management, and the system will greatly affect the process of case management activities.

Status and skills of case managers

Deriving from the theory of case management’s skills, this study assesses the proficiency and confidence of case managers in some of the following skills: communication (including listening, asking questions, establishing relationships skills, etc.), consulting, coordination skills of different resources and service mobilization, and networking. These are the basic skills of a case manager.

Enthusiasm and interest in working environment play an extremely crucial role in human activities in general and the case management profession in particular. It will give rise to positivity in the professional activities for case managers, which can increase working capacity, stimulate the desire to act and act quickly and in an innovative way in case management profession. The actual survey on the enthusiasm and interest in the work of case managers is presented in Table 3.8.

Table 3. Status of skills of case managers

Manifestations	Medium score	Level	Answer options (%)				
			Totally disagree	Basically disagree	Partially agree	Agree basically	Totally agree
I am proficient in the use of communication skills	3.98	4	0	0	20.5	45.7	33.8
I am proficient in the use of counseling skills	4.25	5	0	0	15	58.8	26.2
I am proficient in the use of linking skills	3.41	first	0	9	22.8	45.6	22.6
I am proficient in the use of resource mobilization skills	3.63	2	0	0	27.4	44.7	27.9
I am proficient in the use of coordination skills	3.83	3	0	6	17.4	48.6	28
Skill	3.82						

The results in Table 3.8 show that the skills of case managers, overall, are average with an average score of 3.82. Among the specific skills of case managers, the consulting skill has the highest score (average score = 4.25). In case management for people with disabilities, good advice is also important.

The second most appreciated skill is communication (average score = 3.98), information collection to planning and execution of the case manager's plan.

The third most valued skill of case managers is coordination (average score = 3.83). Next, the skill of resource mobilization (average score of 3.63) and the weakest is networking (average score = 3.41).

Actual status and attitude of case managers

The attitude of case managers also influences significantly on the effectiveness of case management tasks. Based on the theoretical basis, this study assesses attitudes based on three aspects. The first is to respect and accept people with disabilities and their families, the second is to have passion and enthusiasm in their work, and the third is to have positive and initiative mindset.

Table 4. Actual status and attitudes of the case managers

Manifestations	medium score	Level	Answer options (%)				
			Totally disagree	Basically disagree	Partially agree	Agree basically	Totally agree
Respect and accept	4.18	3	0	0	16.5	49.6	33.9
Enthusiastic, passionate	4.55	first	0	0	9	31.2	59.8
Positive, proactive	4.38	2	0	0	12.4	36.4	51.2
<i>Attitude</i>	4.37						

In general, the attitude of the case managers in the case management process towards people with disabilities is good with an adequate score of 4.37. In which the highest expression in the attitude of case managers is passion and enthusiasm (average score = 4.55). Enthusiasm and interest in work play an extremely important role in human activities in general and case management profession in particular. It will give rise to positivity in the professional activities for case managers, which can increase working capacity, stimulate the desire to act and act quickly and in an innovative way in case management profession.

The positive attitude and initiative mindset of the case managers in work occupy a fairly high average score of 4.38. The fact that case managers are proactive and try to find a good solution to the disabled’s problems will greatly affect the improvement of case management tasks for them as well as before doing anything. Case managers often have a specific plan that will avoid mistakes, thereby improving the task of case management when managing cases for people with disabilities is crucial.

The third manifestation of the case manager's attitude is respect and acceptance of people with disabilities, although lower than the above two aspects, it still reaches a high level, with an average score of 4.18.

3. CONCLUSION

An assessment on the current situation of influencing factors showed that the professional knowledge and professional skills of case managers were not good, while the professional attitude was appropriate. Policies for people with disabilities and the number of case managers are lacking and inconsistent, and local resources and services remained limited, unable to meet the needs of people with disabilities.

The influence of factors on case management tasks shows that professional skills and professional knowledge factors have the strongest influence on case management tasks of case managers.

Therefore, the case managers need to have passion, interest and enthusiasm in assisting people with disabilities and should always be ready to participate in developing their professional profession.

The case managers should always show their respect for people with disabilities and their families, identifying the process of assisting people with disabilities and aligning with the needs of people with disabilities.

The institutions managing those case managers need to create opportunities for them to be trained and improvised to increase their professional qualifications, such as creating conditions for them to participate in short-term and long-term training courses; to

participate in conferences and seminars for exchanging knowledge and experiences on counseling for disabled children's families, to participate in counseling classes conducted by experts at local and global level.

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